

1 Re-folded structure of syn-orogenic granitoids: a marker
2 for rheological evolution of cooling extending crust

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17 granitoids; Orogenic collapse; Variscan orogen

18

19 **Abstract**

20 This contribution discusses about the rheological and kinematic frameworks necessary
21 to produce recumbent and upright folds from syn-orogenic granitic massifs that were

22 formed during an early stage of magma genesis related to the onset of a migmatitic
23 dome. Syn-kinematic granitoids occurring within the high-grade infrastructure of the
24 Padrón migmatitic dome (NW Iberia) are deformed into large-scale recumbent folds
25 that are later affected by upright folds. Petrostructural analysis of a selected area of this
26 dome reveals that after a period of crustal thickening, NNW-directed extensional flow
27 gave way to recumbent folds and penetrative axial plane foliation. Superimposed
28 subhorizontal compression resulted in upright folds. A closer view into the dynamics of
29 the dome allows exploring the factors that may condition the nucleation of folds with
30 contrasting geometries during progressive deformation of molten continental crust. The
31 formation of folds affecting syn-kinematic granitoids suggests a cooling metamorphic
32 path in migmatitic domes. Active and passive folding mechanisms require a
33 crystallizing (cooling) magma to nucleate folds. A more competent metamorphic host
34 inhibits fold nucleation from much less competent magmas. As it crystallizes, magma
35 becomes more rigid (competent), and approaches viscosity values of its host. Passive
36 folding is favored when no significant contrast exist between magma and host, so it is
37 more likely shortly after magma genesis and emplacement. Under dominant
38 subhorizontal flow, passive folding would produce isoclinal, somewhat irregular,
39 recumbent geometries. Further magma cooling introduces a shift into the rheological
40 behavior of partially molten crust. Thereon, crystallizing magma bodies would represent
41 significant competence contrasts relative to their host. Then, buckling is the more likely
42 folding mechanism, and the geometry of resulting folds changes. More regular, upright
43 buckle folds occur after significant cooling.

44

45 **1. Introduction**

46 Granitoid bodies are a component of the Earth's crust and common in collisional
47 orogeny (Vanderhaeghe, 2009; Brown, 2013). Crustal anatexis, melt extraction, ascent,
48 and emplacement of granitic magma are closely related to deformation (e.g., Brown and
49 Solar, 1998; Druguet and Hutton, 1998; Vigneresse and Tikoff, 1999; Rosenberg,
50 2004). During progressive crystallization from crystal suspension fluids (isotropic to
51 weakly anisotropic), granitic bodies accumulate strain and structures according to
52 deformation occurred in the process (Hutton, 1988). Magmatic fabrics are easily reset
53 and usually reflect only the last increment of strain. Stresses at this early stage may
54 derive from internal (internally driven magma flow) and/or external (related to tectonic
55 setting) forces, the latter gaining importance throughout the emplacement process, while
56 magma turns into a rigid (stiffer) material (e.g., Paterson et al., 1998).

57 The primary geometry of granitoid massifs is conditioned by the structure and
58 rheology of their host, by the viscosity contrast between host and magma, and by the
59 stress field during emplacement (Pitcher, 1979, 1993; Ramberg, 1981; Castro, 1987;
60 Hutton, 1988; Brown, 1994; Vigneresse, 1995a; Petford et al., 2000). Most models
61 proposed for the emplacement of granites consider the development of dilatant or
62 tensional sites in relation to shear zones, either in strike-slip systems (e.g., D'Lemos et
63 al., 1992; Aranguren et al., 1997; Kratinová et al., 2007; Sant'Ovaia et al., 2010) or in
64 extensional settings (e.g., Aranguren and Tubía, 1992; Clemens and Mawer, 1992;
65 Díaz-Alvarado et al., 2012). Mechanisms suggested for magma emplacement may
66 include doming, diapirism (Dixon, 1975), nested diapirism (Paterson and Vernon,
67 1995), ballooning (Ramsay, 1989), stoping and in-situ assimilation (Daly, 1903;
68 Paterson et al., 2008), cauldron subsidence (Johnson, 1966), ascent through propagating
69 dykes (Clemens and Mawer, 1992), growth of plutons by progressive emplacement of

70 sheets during crust extension (Hutton et al., 1990) or transpression (Olivier et al., 2016),
71 or favored by crustal boudinage (D'Eramo et al., 2013).

72 The structure of granitoid massifs has been studied via extensive field work,
73 microscopic observations, and using geophysical data such as anisotropy of magnetic
74 susceptibility and/or gravity data (e.g., Guineberteau et al., 1987; Vigneresse, 1995a,
75 1995b; Améglio and Vigneresse, 2000; Kratinová et al., 2007; Burchardt et al., 2010).
76 Modeling has also contributed to explaining the structure of granitic massifs (e.g.,
77 Roman-Berdiel et al., 1995; Corti et al., 2005). In general terms, mapping and structural
78 analysis of syn-orogenic granitoids suggest a more lensoid structure with respect to the
79 later, late- to post-tectonic plutons, which tend to show more equidimensional shape in
80 map view. On the other hand, geophysical data support that even post-tectonic granitic
81 massifs with a rounded shape in map view may also have a gross lensoid, sheet-like
82 shape in 3D (e.g., Aranguren et al., 2003; Valle Aguado et al., 2017).

83 Collisional orogens are characterized by multiple stages of tectonic evolution,
84 which commonly lead to superimposition and interference of deformation phases. In
85 this light, several phases of deformation may contribute to the final geometry of a given
86 granitoid massif, the structure of which would depend not only on processes operating
87 during its ascent and emplacement, but also on those that may follow. Therefore, syn-
88 orogenic granitoids can record multiple stages of deformation. Ongoing deformation in
89 partially molten crust is considered a relevant factor controlling the migration and
90 accumulation of melt in the crust (e.g., McLellan, 1988; Sawyer, 1994; Brown and
91 Solar, 1998; Vigneresse and Burg, 2000; Brown, 2007; Hasalová et al., 2008; Weinberg
92 and Mark, 2008). If that holds correct, structures (including granitoid bodies) formed at
93 an earlier stage during the evolution of migmatized crust are expected to be modified by
94 subsequent deformation. When such deformation produces folds at a large scale, an

95 examination of the rheology of partially molten crust is possible. This is because active
96 and/or passive mechanisms of folding operate under specific rheological conditions, the
97 resulting fold geometries being somewhat predictable (e.g., Ramsay, 1967; Hudleston,
98 1973; Sanderson, 1982; Ramsay and Huber, 1987; Ghosh, 1993; Fossen, 2010).

99 The formation of migmatite-cored domes encompass subhorizontal ductile
100 shearing and granitic magmatism, a combination that results in penetrative foliation
101 contouring the domes (dipping radially away its core) and in sheet-like granitic massifs
102 (laccoliths) subconcordant and/or wrapped around by the foliation (e.g., Mezger and
103 Passchier, 2003; Whitney et al., 2004; Charles et al., 2009; Vanderhaeghe, 2009;
104 McFadden et al., 2010; Brown et al., 2011). The presence of sheared and/or intensively
105 folded migmatitic banding is a common feature in high-grade rocks. In the case of
106 recumbent folds, this observation implies that deformation extends longer than the early
107 stages of melt segregation, migration, and accumulation taking place in migmatized
108 terranes, thus suggesting that stresses, whatever the source, are present over the time
109 period of melting events (Sawyer, 2001). This critical observation opens the possibility
110 that much larger melt accumulations (i.e. granitoid massifs) could be similarly affected
111 by superimposed deformation.

112 Here we present a field-based study on the internal structure of a selected section
113 of the Padrón migmatitic dome (NW Iberia), and provide a closer view into the
114 dynamics of this dome. This dome is characterized by km-scale recumbent folds and
115 later upright folds, both affecting migmatites and regional syn-orogenic granitoids.
116 Since this is not a commonly described scenario in collapsing orogenic systems, we
117 introduce an extended discussion about the evolving rheological and kinematic
118 conditions necessary to produce folds with contrasting geometries at the expense of
119 large granitoid bodies, and how those conditions are met by the study area. With this

120 contribution, we improve our understanding of tectonic processes related to syn-
121 orogenic magmatism by providing a case example where the final structure of syn-
122 orogenic granitoids is mildly conditioned by the processes related to melt generation,
123 ascent and emplacement (as usually admitted), but largely controlled by superimposed
124 deformation taking place during final cooling and crystallization.

125

126 **2. Geological setting**

127 The NW section of the Iberian Massif preserves a thrust stack formed during the
128 progressive collision of Gondwana and Laurussia in Devonian-Carboniferous times
129 (Fig. 1; Matte, 1991; Martínez Catalán et al., 1997; Ribeiro et al., 2007; Arenas et al.,
130 2014; Díez Fernández et al., 2016). The peripheral and outer Paleozoic paleogeographic
131 domains of Gondwana are located on top of the pile, whereas its progressively inner
132 domains lie in lower structural position (Fig. 2; Martínez Catalán et al., 2007, 2009).
133 Except for some ophiolitic assemblages, the tectonic pile is made of tectonic slices with
134 continental crust affinity.

135 The uppermost part of the NW Iberia tectonic pile is a far travelled set of
136 allochthonous units. They include ophiolites and high-pressure metamorphic rocks and
137 constitute an obducted suture zone between two outboard sections of Gondwana that
138 were separated by an ephemeral marine basin (Arenas et al., 2016, and references
139 therein). The allochthonous pile is emplaced on top of a series of thrust sheets
140 collectively referred to as Parautochthon (Farias et al., 1987; Ribeiro et al., 1990;
141 Martínez Catalán et al., 1996; Dias da Silva et al., 2015). The Parautochthon is
142 considered an inner part of the margin of Gondwana relative to the allochthonous units
143 (e.g., Díez Fernández et al., 2012a), and separates them from the underlying
144 Autochthon. The latter is largely exposed in the so-called Central Iberian Zone, and

145 includes marine successions deposited closer to mainland Gondwana (Valladares et al.,
146 1993; Martínez Catalán et al., 1997; Ugidos et al., 1997; Gutiérrez-Marco et al., 2002;
147 Robardet, 2003).

148 Variscan thrust tectonics in NW Iberia (e.g., Pérez-Estaún et al., 1991; Martínez
149 Catalán et al., 1997) was followed by a stage of gravitational collapse (e.g., Escuder
150 Viruete et al., 1994; Martínez Catalán et al., 2002), which initiated with a thermal
151 relaxation event (e.g., Alcock et al., 2015) and the onset of viscous flow
152 accommodating subhorizontal extension throughout an overthickened lithosphere (e.g.,
153 Gómez Barreiro et al., 2010; Díez Fernández et al., 2012b; Martínez Catalán et al.,
154 2014). Extensional flow was influenced, and then progressively captured and replaced
155 by a phase dominated by strike-slip tectonics (Díez Fernández et al., 2012b; Díez
156 Fernández and Pereira, 2016), which generated discrete transcurrent shear zones,
157 upright folds and subvertical faulting under transpression (e.g., Iglesias Ponce de Leon
158 and Choukroune, 1980; González Clavijo et al., 1991; Villar Alonso et al., 1992; Llana-
159 Fúnez and Marcos, 2001; Díez Fernández and Martínez Catalán, 2012).

160 In the hinterland of the orogen, the resulting post-nappe emplacement geometry
161 is defined by structural domes and basins formed during the extensional stage, and then
162 refolded (tightened) by superimposed compression (Fig. 2). Late deformation affecting
163 the domes has conferred them the appearance of individual and sometimes narrow
164 migmatitic belts trending parallel to the structural grain of the orogen. The core of the
165 domes (infrastructure) is the site of abundant magmatism and high-grade rocks
166 (Martínez et al., 1988, 1990; Martínez Catalán et al., 2014, and references therein), and
167 it is usually separated from the mantling metamorphic series (suprastructure) by low-
168 angle normal faults (Martínez Catalán et al., 2002; Díez Montes, 2007; Gómez Barreiro
169 et al., 2010; Díez Fernández et al., 2012b).

170 The overall metamorphic evolution observed in the core of the domes starts with
171 a Barrovian-type event, including the growth of garnet, staurolite, and even kyanite in
172 the metasedimentary rocks. It is followed by a temperature-dominated event typified by
173 the breakdown of former mineral phases, a grain size increase, and the growth of
174 sillimanite, andalusite, and/or cordierite and K-feldspar (Atherton et al., 1974; Godinho,
175 1974; Oen, 1974; Gil Ibarra, 1982; Marquínez and Klein, 1982; Martínez and Rolet,
176 1988; Martínez et al., 1990; Díez Montes, 2007; Rubio Pascual et al., 2015). The first
177 metamorphism represents an early stage related to crustal thickening (fold and thrust
178 tectonics), while the low-P/high-T event accounts for the exhumation of the core of the
179 domes, which is associated with lateral spreading of overlying metamorphic nappes and
180 gravity-driven lithosphere extension (Martínez Catalán et al., 2002; Díez Montes, 2007;
181 Gómez Barreiro et al., 2010; Díez Fernández et al., 2012b).

182

183 *2.1. The Padrón migmatitic dome: an overview*

184 The Padrón migmatitic dome occupies the axial zone of the Variscan orogen
185 exposed in NW Iberia. It constitutes an exposure of high-grade metamorphic rocks and
186 granitoids that is situated between the allochthonous complexes of Órdenes and
187 Malpica-Tui (Fig. 2). The suprastructure of the dome is occupied by the allochthonous
188 complexes (see extended revision of their tectonometamorphic evolution by Arenas et
189 al., 2016). The infrastructure includes the Parautochthon and Autochthon, both largely
190 transformed during Variscan high-grade metamorphism and intruded by granitoids. The
191 Parautochthon in this area consists of a metasedimentary rock sequence with mica
192 schists, quartz-rich schists, migmatites (mostly metatexites), and minor quartzites and
193 graphite-bearing schists (Paraño Group; as defined by Marquínez García, 1981). The
194 Autochthon is dominated by paragneisses and migmatites (metatexites, diatexites and

195 nebulites). But in this region, it contains bodies of either biotite augen-orthogneisses,
196 biotite fine-grained orthogneisses or amphibole-biotite fine-grained orthogneisses.
197 Some lenses of amphibolite can be found. Despite the intense metamorphic overprints,
198 it can be recognized that the metasedimentary rock sequence of the Autochthon was
199 made of an alternation of immature sandstone and pelites (no clear Bouma cycles were
200 recognized), with some minor and very thin layers of black pelites.

201 The Padrón dome is approximately elongated in the N-S direction. Its axial zone
202 is parallel to the dominant regional structures of the region, which are partly controlled
203 by late Variscan strike-slip shear zones cutting across the nappe stack and the dome
204 itself. Towards the north, the infrastructural core of the dome varies its average width of
205 exposure from 25 km to 2-3 km due to the narrowing effect of late strike-slip shear
206 zones (Díez Fernández and Martínez Catalán, 2012). The southern branch of the dome
207 trends NNW-SSE, whereas the northern branch trends NNE-SSW, thus defining the
208 arcuate structure of the Ibero-Armorican orocline.

209 In the northern part of the dome, supra- and infrastructure are separated by the
210 Pico Sacro detachment, a NNW-directed extensional fault that also cuts sections of the
211 suprastructure of the dome to the E (Figs. 2 and 3; Martínez Catalán et al., 2002; Gómez
212 Barreiro et al., 2010). The Redondela-Beariz detachment marks the boundary between
213 supra- and infrastructure in the southern branch of the dome (Fig. 2). The hanging wall
214 of this extensional fault moved to the SSE, thus defining a divergent geometry for the
215 extensional flow operating within the dome (Díez Fernández et al., 2012b). The
216 Bembibre-Ceán detachment is a NNW-directed extensional fault that is cut by the Pico
217 Sacro detachment, and defines an internal regional contact within the allochthonous
218 units (Figs. 2 and 3; Díez Fernández et al., 2012b). The Pico Sacro, Redondela-Beariz
219 and Bembibre-Ceán faults occur at both the eastern and western limb of the Padrón

220 dome, meaning that late upright folds, i.e., the folds that developed in relation to late
221 strike-slip tectonics in the region, eventually affected these faults and, therefore, the
222 dome itself (Díez Fernández, 2011).

223 The main foliation observed in both the allochthonous complexes and its relative
224 autochthon accommodates to the dome structure of Padrón. Such structure may be cut
225 by post-kinematic granitoids. However, the contacts and internal tectonic fabrics of a
226 significant part of the granitoids occurring within the dome are subconcordant with the
227 main foliation observed in their country rocks. The regional structural analysis of the
228 latter type of granitoids presented here particularly focus on those that are exposed in
229 the northern part of the dome (Figs. 2, 3a and 4).

230

231 *2.2 Petrography of main rock types*

232 The migmatitic metapelites of the study area consist of quartz, biotite,
233 plagioclase, K-feldspar, sillimanite, muscovite, andalusite, and minor amounts of
234 cordierite, garnet, staurolite, tourmaline, apatite, zircon, chlorite and opaque minerals
235 (Fig. 5a). The leucosomes contain medium- to coarse-grained quartz, feldspar,
236 plagioclase and rare muscovite, biotite and garnet. These minerals but garnet show
237 shape-preferred orientation parallel to the main foliation and display evidence of solid-
238 state deformation, including internal deformation and recrystallization, grain-size
239 reduction, foliation anastomosing, microcline twinning, myrmekite, and boudinage of
240 competent minerals (feldspar; boudin necks filled with feldspar, plagioclase, quartz and
241 mica). Leucosomes occur as branching veins, minor pods and thin layers parallel to the
242 main foliation and/or bedding. Melanosomes may contain andalusite, but are enriched in
243 biotite, and sometimes in sillimanite. They define a penetrative foliation, and alternate
244 with layers richer in medium- to fine-grained quartz, feldspar and plagioclase. Fibrolitic

245 sillimanite can be trapped within andalusite porphyroblasts and within muscovite.
246 Muscovite usually occur as non-oriented (post-kinematic) flakes superimposed to the
247 main foliation. Low-temperature transformations include the replacement of biotite by
248 chlorite, feldspar or aluminum silicate by muscovite, or the growth of chlorite filling
249 boudin necks between fragments of andalusite and parallel to the main foliation (Fig.
250 5b).

251 The biotite augen-orthogneisses consist of quartz, K-feldspar (augen),
252 plagioclase, biotite, and muscovite, with minor zircon, apatite, sillimanite, garnet, rutile,
253 and opaque minerals. The fine-grained biotite orthogneisses include quartz, plagioclase,
254 K-feldspar, and biotite, with minor amounts of muscovite, zircon, apatite, epidote, and
255 opaque minerals. The amphibole-biotite fine-grained orthogneisses mainly contain
256 plagioclase and amphibole (hornblende), plus variable amounts of titanite, K-feldspar,
257 apatite, opaque minerals, and chlorite. Feldspar, plagioclase, quartz, amphibole, mica,
258 sillimanite, opaques, epidote and chlorite in these gneisses show shape-preferred
259 orientation parallel to the main foliation (Fig. 5c). Feldspar, plagioclase, quartz, mica
260 and amphibole display evidence of solid-state deformation, including grain-size
261 reduction, internal deformation and recrystallization, microcline twinning, and
262 myrmekite.

263 The granitic massifs of the study area are syn-kinematic relative to the Variscan
264 orogeny (Capdevila et al., 1973; Castro et al., 2002). The syn-kinematic granites can be
265 subdivided into a granite-diatexite ensemble, bodies of two-mica granites, and a massif
266 of granodiorites. The granites contain quartz, K-feldspar, plagioclase, biotite,
267 muscovite, and minor amounts of apatite, zircon, rutile, sillimanite and opaque
268 minerals, whereas the granodiorites are made of quartz, plagioclase, K-feldspar, biotite,
269 and minor and variable amounts of muscovite, apatite, zircon, tourmaline, opaques, and

270 epidote. The granite-diatexite ensemble shows fine to coarse grain size, dominant
271 allotriomorphic-granular to hypidiomorphic (even porphyritic for feldspar) texture, and
272 dispersed patches of metatexite and diatexite. The granite-diatexite ensemble is usually
273 transitional into the migmatitic metasedimentary host. The proportion and size of lenses
274 of leucogranite in the metatexites increase towards the main body of granite-diatexite
275 (Fig. 5d). The two-mica granites show a similar range of textures to the granite-
276 diatexite. They are more homogeneous in grain size (medium) and mineral proportions,
277 but lack of metatexite enclaves. The granodiorites have medium grain size, but fine-
278 grained facies exist. Textures range between hypidiomorphic-granular to
279 allotriomorphic, being porphyritic for feldspar.

280 The fabrics in the granitoids range from facies showing preferred orientation of
281 minerals to facies with vague or no preferred orientation. Planar fabrics in the granite-
282 diatexite ensemble are consistently parallel to that of the diatexites, metatexites, lenses
283 of leucogranite and schists and paragneisses nearby, but never define compositional
284 banding. In the granite-diatexite ensemble and in the lenses of leucogranite, biotite,
285 muscovite, and elongate feldspar and quartz define the fabric at the mesoscale.
286 Subgrains of quartz, subgrains of plagioclase and subgrains of feldspar, along with
287 aggregates of muscovite and biotite, represent additional foliation markers at the
288 microscale (Fig. 5e), and suggest solid-state deformation. The main planar fabric is also
289 defined by aligned euhedral crystals of feldspar that are imbricated with other similar
290 grains. The two-mica granites does not show penetrative foliation, only a poor to
291 moderate alignment of elongate euhedral feldspar and biotite. The boundaries of the
292 massifs of two-mica granites cut the main foliation of the study area, as well as some
293 contacts within the allochthon (Figs. 3a and 4). Planar fabrics marked by the preferred
294 orientation of subeuhedral feldspar and mica aggregates characterize the granodiorites.

295 Part of those feldspars are porphyritic, does not show internal deformation (or rather
296 weak deformation), and may be imbricated with other crystals (Fig. 5f). Some
297 exposures show banded structure consisting of darker (biotite-richer) and lighter bands
298 parallel to the planar fabric (Fig. 5f).

299

300 **3. Phases of deformation**

301 The core of the Padrón dome is affected by three main phases of deformation
302 (Díez Fernández et al., 2012b). The first one (D₁) can only be observed at the
303 microscale, as relicts after pervasive post-D₁ deformation and metamorphism. The
304 second one (D₂) spreads out through almost all lithologies that occur within the Padrón
305 dome but in some later granitoids, and is mainly represented by a pervasive foliation
306 (S₂). The third one (D₃) is derived from the folded geometry of S₂ both at the regional
307 scale (Figs. 3b and 6), defining the Padrón dome itself (see below), and at local scale,
308 through the development of crenulation cleavages (S₃) and associated shear zones.
309 Figures 3c and d, and 7 show a compilation of structural data (planes and lines) from the
310 northern part of the Padrón dome. These data have been plotted separately, grouping
311 interrelated data into different plots following geographic criteria. Given the arched
312 structural grain of the study area, plots were produced for different areas from north to
313 south, in order to avoid data noise.

314

315 *3.1. D₁ – Vestiges of early deformation*

316 D₁ is inferred by means of a tectonic fabric (S₁) preserved either as a disrupted
317 crenulated foliation and/or as an internal foliation trapped within post-D₁ porphyroblasts
318 (Fig. 8a) (Díez Fernández, 2011). Relicts of S₁ can be potentially found in any outcrop
319 of the metasedimentary rocks of the relative autochthon, particularly in metapelitic

320 lithologies. Although the metaigneous rocks must have experienced a similar
321 tectonometamorphic evolution, S_1 was not clearly recognized in them. In the
322 metasedimentary rocks, the D_1 mineral assemblage may consist of quartz, white mica,
323 biotite, plagioclase, garnet, staurolite, tourmaline, and opaque minerals (e.g., Fig. 5b),
324 likely formed under amphibolite facies conditions (M_1).

325

326 *3.2. D_2 – Main foliation and related structures*

327 In the metasedimentary rocks, S_2 ranges between a schistosity (crenulation
328 cleavage; Fig. 8b) and a gneissic banding (Fig. 5a), turning progressively into a
329 migmatitic banding towards the granitic massifs (Fig. 8c). In this transition, metatexites
330 (Fig. 5d), diatexites (Fig. 8c), and nebulites can be observed.

331 The D_2 mineral assemblages may contain quartz, biotite, white mica,
332 plagioclase, andalusite, sillimanite, K-feldspar, cordierite, tourmaline, and opaque
333 minerals in the metapelitic terms (Fig. 5a), whereas in the metaigneous rocks, it
334 contains quartz-feldspathic and mica-rich bands (Fig. 5c), with some green amphibole
335 and rare garnet. The lenses of leucogranite exhibit penetrative foliation (solid-state
336 deformation), which is concordant with the main foliation of the metamorphic host (S_2 ;
337 Fig. 5d). The larger granite-diatexite massifs have a similar and even concordant S_2
338 fabric (Fig. 8d). The structure of these massifs seems tabular, at least in part, due to the
339 parallelism between their boundaries and S_2 . Such structural parallelism, as well as the
340 compatibility of D_2 metamorphism (M_2 ; high-T/low-P) in the host rocks and the P-T
341 conditions of magma emplacement suggest a syn-kinematic character for these
342 granitoids (following Paterson et al., 1989). Migmatization (Fig. 8c), reinjection of local
343 melts (Fig. 8e), and the presence of sillimanite in an andalusite-bearing foliation
344 affecting these partially molten rocks have been considered as the result of high-T

345 metamorphism during decompression up to the upper crust (Díez Fernández et al.,
346 2012b).

347 S₂ has low- to moderate-dipping, but it may show near-vertical geometry due to
348 D₃ folding (Figs. 3c, 7a, and 7f). S₂ is a composite planar fabric formed after two
349 foliation-forming events (see extended description provided by Díez Fernández et al.,
350 2017). The early-D₂ fabric is associated with the development of the migmatitic banding
351 and probably an incipient tectonic banding (proto-S₂). The S₂ *sensu stricto* affects the
352 migmatitic banding, as the latter is deformed under solid-state conditions and affected
353 by D₂ recumbent folds (Fig. 8b). S₂ is axial planar to these folds, which trend NE-SW
354 (F₂; Fig. 6e) and also affect granitic dikes that cut across the migmatites (Fig. 8e).

355 S₂ shows a mineral lineation (mostly defined by micas) that matches the trend of
356 stretched quartz, feldspar grains, and the elongated shape of andalusite, melanocratic
357 mineral aggregates (biotite, sillimanite and cordierite in the migmatites; amphibole and
358 biotite in the orthogneisses) and leucosomes (Fig. 8f). All of them are considered
359 markers of a stretching lineation (L_{2s}), which is generally oblique to F₂ and trends
360 NNE-SSW to the north of Corcoesto up to Caión (Fig. 3d; northern half of Fig. 3a), N-S
361 to the west of Agualada (Fig. 7b; southern half of Fig. 3a), and NNW-SSE in the A
362 Pereira area (Fig. 7e; central and southern half of Fig. 4). This progressive shift in the
363 lineation trend fits the arched structure of the region, and so it defines a small section of
364 the late Variscan Ibero-Armorican orocline. The minerals in the syn-kinematic granitic
365 rocks, together with elongated enclaves and restites, define a mineral and stretching
366 lineation over S₂ planes. Such lineation coincides with that of their metamorphic host.
367 In both the metasedimentary rocks and granitoids, foliation is well formed, but a linear
368 fabric is generally less intense in the case of the granitoids. Markedly linear fabrics were
369 not found in either the metamorphic host or the granitoids, although foliated rocks

370 lacking of lineation do exist. Accordingly, S-L tectonites seem to dominate in the study
371 area. No spatial variation of fabric types has been observed respect to major structures.

372 S_2 is accompanied by the development of asymmetric shape fabrics, such as σ -
373 type objects (e.g., individual mineral grains or leucosomes; Fig. 5d and 8a), mica-fish,
374 SC composite foliations, C' fabrics, and δ -type structures (Fig. 9a), which consistently
375 indicate north-directed tectonic flow. In the areas less affected by later ductile
376 deformation, L_{2s} is approximately contained in the sections showing maximum vorticity
377 (Vorticity Profile Plane), which were roughly constrained using apparent and normal
378 sections to local, minor structures (mostly σ -type objects). Sections normal (or roughly
379 normal) to L_{2s} showed maximum symmetry, whereas the sections parallel (or roughly
380 parallel) to L_{2s} showed maximum asymmetry. Consequently, the stretching lineation is
381 normal to the vorticity vector. Kinematic criteria associated with asymmetric S_2
382 structures, together with the trend of L_{2s} , indicate either top-to-the-NNW, -N, or -NNE
383 shear sense, depending on the local lineation trend (Figs. 3d, 7b and 7e).

384

385 *3.3. D_3 – Later upright folds*

386 S_2 and their associated structures are heterogeneously affected by upright folds
387 (D_3). These folds show a generally open geometry, but they turn into a tighter one
388 towards the north (Fig. 8c), as the exposure of the granitic core of the dome becomes
389 narrower, and also towards the east, in the vicinity of the eastern boundary of a syn-
390 kinematic granodiorite (Negreira granodiorite). The axial planes of D_3 folds (S_3) follow
391 the regional trend of the long axis of the dome. S_3 strikes NE-SW to the north of
392 Corcoesto up to Caión (Fig. 3c; northern half of Fig. 3a), N-S to the west of Agualada
393 (Fig. 7a; southern half of Fig. 3a), NNW-SSE to the north of Santa Comba (Fig. 7c;
394 northern half of Fig. 4), and NNW-SSE to N-S in the A Pereira area (Fig. 7d; central

395 and southern part of Fig. 4). D₃ fold axes (F₃) show identical trend variation. South-
396 plunging folds dominate in the southern part of the study area (Figs. 7c and 7d),
397 whereas in the northern part the plunge of D₃ folds varies from north- to south-directed
398 (Figs. 3c and 7a).

399 The domains with tighter D₃ folds usually show subvertical crenulation cleavage
400 (S₃), which may be the most penetrative fabric in some cases. If present, S₃ consists of
401 quartz + chlorite + muscovite + opaques and reoriented S₂ minerals. Some minerals,
402 such as muscovite, are aligned with F₃.

403 The massif of syn-kinematic granodiorites shows a subvertical planar fabric that
404 is consistently parallel to the axial planes of D₃ folds and to the S₃ crenulation cleavage,
405 and that is usually oblique to S₂ (Fig. 4). Such fabric is defined by the preferred
406 orientation of quartz, biotite, elongate feldspar and plagioclase, and rare muscovite. This
407 foliation is also defined by subgrain boundaries of quartz, plagioclase and feldspar
408 crystals, and by recrystallized aggregates of biotite. The presence of aligned, partially
409 imbricated, and not internally deformed euhedral crystals of feldspar in this fabric
410 suggests that solid-state deformation is combined with a component of magmatic flow
411 (e.g., Paterson et al., 1989; Vernon, 2000). Euhedral feldspars are frequently aligned
412 defining a subhorizontal mineral lineation that roughly matches the trend of F₃. S₃ and
413 the fabric in these granodiorites are tentatively considered as equivalent, meaning that
414 these granodiorites would represent syn-D₃ granitoids *sensu lato*.

415

416 **4. The Santa Comba recumbent antiform**

417 The regional structure of the Santa Comba area is defined by the interference
418 between two major folds: the Santa Comba recumbent antiform and the later upright
419 Padrón antiform (Figs. 3b, 6a and 6b).

420 The Padrón antiform marks the axial zone of the Padrón dome and folds the
421 regional foliation (S_2). Some lithological contacts that are parallel to S_2 are folded in a
422 similar way, and thus they depict upright fold contours in map view. Good examples of
423 this folding can be found to the east of Caión (RP-1; Fig. 3a), south of Corcoesto (RP-2;
424 Fig. 3a), northwest of Santa Comba (RP-1; Fig. 4), or south of A Pereira (RP-2; Fig. 4).
425 These examples represent single exposures of the hinge zone of the Padrón antiform,
426 but parasitic folds at all scales accompany this major structure.

427 The first hint to recognize the Santa Comba recumbent antiform is that similar
428 layers of granitic rocks occur both on top (RP-2; Fig. 4) and under (RP-1; Fig. 4) a
429 series of rather monotonous paragneisses of the Autochthon. Duplication of these layers
430 of granitoid cannot be explained by thrusts because the pattern of repetition is not
431 asymmetric: schists of the Parautochthon rest on top of the upper granitoid layer (RP-3
432 and 4; Fig. 4) whereas gneisses of the Autochthon occur on top of the lower granitoid
433 layer (RP-1; Fig. 4). A symmetric pattern expected for folds is not evident either,
434 because the schists of the Parautochthon are found on top the granitoids (e.g., RP-3; Fig.
435 3a) and no clear exposures of those same schists occur beneath them. Given the lack of
436 reliable way-up criteria within the metasedimentary rock series (note we are dealing
437 with gneisses and deformed granitoids), a geometrical approach to the regional structure
438 of deformed igneous massifs backed up with that of their host seems adequate (e.g.,
439 Díez Fernández and Martínez Catalán, 2009).

440 Field evidence (e.g., development of penetrative foliation and even stretching
441 lineation) suggest that the granitic massifs were affected by flattening and stretching
442 during D_2 . The boundaries of the largest massifs in map view are remarkably parallel to
443 S_2 . Accordingly, those contacts would probably trace the boundaries of sheet-like
444 bodies of granitoid, i.e. regional laccoliths adapted to the planar regional anisotropy

445 defined by the main foliation. But those same contacts can also be oblique or
446 perpendicular to S_2 , particularly in zones where they are characterized by a fold-like
447 map pattern that resembles a fold hinge.

448 The two main layers of D_2 syn-kinematic granitoids (RP-1 and 2, respectively;
449 Fig. 4) merge towards the north and define a fold-like structure that dips to the east
450 (according to S_2) and host the gneisses and migmatites of the Autochthon (RP-5; Fig.
451 4). This structure is repeated few kilometers to the south, in the western limb of the
452 Padrón antiform (RP-6; Fig. 4), but including some additional minor fold-like
453 structures. Altogether, they are interpreted as the hinge zone of a major recumbent fold
454 that shows hook shaped interference pattern with the D_3 Padrón antiform (Fig. 6a and
455 6b). From a geometrical perspective, S_2 is axial planar to this fold, as also observed for
456 recumbent folds at the mesoscale (see section 3.2). As a result, that major fold is
457 considered as a D_2 macrostructure. Minor D_2 asymmetric folds support this statement.
458 The upper limb of this major recumbent fold preserves a regional tectonostratigraphic
459 sequence in normal position, i.e. Parautochthon on top of Autochthon (e.g., RP-7; Fig.
460 4). Accordingly, and given the top-to-the-NNW kinematics associated with D_2 (Figs.
461 3d, 7b and 7e; see section 3.2), the fold is considered a NW-verging antiform, and will
462 be referred to as the Santa Comba recumbent antiform.

463 The two main occurrences of the hinge zone of the Santa Comba recumbent
464 antiform (RP-5 and 6; Fig. 4) are aligned following the trend of F_2 , i.e. NNE-SSW (Fig.
465 7e), defining an angle less than 90° counterclockwise in relation to the long axis of the
466 Padrón dome. Some other minor asymmetric folds can be mapped along the granitoid-
467 metasedimentary rock contact that defines the normal limb of the Santa Comba
468 recumbent antiform (e.g., RP-8-10; Fig. 4). A thin body of orthogneisses located at the
469 hinge zone of this antiform displays typical sinuous contacts for recumbent folds (RP-

470 11; Fig. 4). The orthogneissic body itself defines a pair of mesoscale D₂ folds, which
471 together depict a reverse limb asymmetry (Fig. 6b). These particular folds occur
472 relatively close to the main normal limb of the Santa Comba recumbent antiform.
473 However, field data such as minor fold asymmetry and crosscutting relationships
474 between S₂ (axial planar to the folds) and previous planar anisotropies indicate the
475 existence of more mesoscale (parasitic) folds within the intrados of the Santa Comba
476 recumbent antiform, despite they are not revealed by contrasting lithologies in map
477 view. Some of the axial traces of those mesoscale folds were constrained by field
478 observations and are represented in Figure 4 (map) and 6b (cross-section).

479 The amplification direction of D₃ (upright) folds lies at high angle to the axial
480 planes of the D₂ (recumbent) folds. Towards the north, the axial plane of the Santa
481 Comba recumbent antiform dips to the north (RP-4; Fig. 3a) and its fold axis trends N-
482 S, thus favoring an additional occurrence of its normal limb at the core of a local, dome-
483 like, D₃ upright fold (RP-2; Fig. 3a). In the central and southern part of the study area
484 (Fig. 4), the fold hinge lines of the recumbent (D₂) and upright (D₃) folds are roughly
485 parallel, with a trend ranging between N-S and NE-SW (Figs. 7d, 7e, 7f). As a result,
486 the most common interference pattern in the study area produces hooks and can be
487 classified as Type-3 (Ramsay, 1967). However, some minor obliquity between D₂ and
488 D₃ fold axes could also produce Type-0₁ refolded structures (Grasemann et al., 2004).

489 From southeast to northwest, the Pico Sacro detachment approaches
490 dramatically to the intrados of the Santa Comba recumbent antiform occupied by the
491 gneisses and migmatites of the Autochthon (RP-5; Fig. 4). Those same gneisses define a
492 great exposure of such intrados over the core of the Padrón antiform to the south,
493 suggesting obliquity between the fault and the recumbent fold. Crosscutting
494 relationships are clearer if we focus on the limbs of the recumbent fold. In the eastern

495 flank of the Padrón dome, the thickness of the layer of granitoid that defines the normal
496 limb of the Santa Comba recumbent antiform varies from several kilometers to the east
497 to less than 200 meters to the west (RP-12; Fig. 4). In the western limb of the Padrón
498 antiform, the aforementioned layer of granitoid and the overlying schists of the
499 Parautochthon are dissected (RP-3; Fig. 4) and attenuated (RP-7; Fig. 4) by the Pico
500 Sacro detachment. This suggests a different dip angle for the detachment relative to the
501 recumbent fold limb. Such difference would imply either a primary higher east-dipping
502 geometry for the fold limb or a primary higher west-dipping geometry for the
503 detachment. The Pico Sacro detachment is considered a NNW-dipping extensional fault
504 (Gómez Barreiro et al., 2010). However, superimposed D₃ upright folding hampers
505 precise restoration of the paleoinclination of the reference (axial) planes of the previous
506 recumbent structures, so an east-dipping component should not be discarded for their
507 primary geometry. In fact, such consideration would fit well with the NNW-directed
508 tectonic flow inferred for D₂ structures, as those folds would verge to the NNW, i.e.
509 they could have had SSE-dipping axial planes.

510

511 **5. Discussion**

512 The formation of structures such as recumbent folds in the core of a migmatitic
513 dome is not a particularly new finding (e.g., Sawyer, 2008 and references therein).
514 Folds may form in extensional settings (e.g., Harris et al., 2002; Fossen et al., 2013;
515 Bastida et al., 2014), even up to the scale of several kilometers (e.g., Platt, 1982;
516 Froitzheim, 1992; Orozco et al., 1997; Arango et al., 2013; Díez Fernández et al., 2013).
517 What it seems less common is that, in the case of the Santa Comba antiform, it is the
518 (large) massifs of syn-kinematic granitoids that are being folded in the course of the
519 regional deformation event to which they are linked. As a result, melt generation and

520 emplacement, and large-scale folding are not too far apart in the evolution of the dome.
521 Since D₂ syn-kinematic granitoids and migmatites are closely related in the study area,
522 it is important to note that D₂ recumbent folding occurred under solid-state conditions,
523 after part of the melt in the migmatites had crystallized. It means that dominant
524 migmatites in this region are folded migmatites, as opposed to fold-structured
525 migmatites. The latter usually develop in the early stages of anatexis, at low fractions of
526 melt, and the folds they exhibit may not be associated with large-scale structures of
527 regional extent.

528 The recognition of a large-scale recumbent fold structure affecting both the D₂
529 syn-kinematic granitoids and their metamorphic host has multiple implications, both
530 regionally and for the understanding of internal mechanisms that may take place inside
531 migmatitic domes.

532

533 *5.1. Deformation conditions during D₂*

534 The development of recumbent folds during D₂ took place in a section of an
535 extending and cooling crust. Unfolding of upright D₃ structures does not constrain the
536 primary dipping direction for S₂, it just indicates the low-dipping geometry of that
537 foliation. The formation of the Padrón dome is characterized by regional divergent flow
538 during D₂. Kinematic criteria associated with the development of S₂ in its northern
539 section (study area) indicate top-to-the-NW shear sense, whereas the southern section of
540 the dome flowed towards the southeast (Díez Fernández et al., 2012b). S₂ pitches
541 towards the upper-crustal sections located to the east (Fig. 2), i.e. under the Gondwanan
542 foreland of the orogen (Cantabrian Zone). This is in agreement with the geometry of a
543 normal fault, which along with the divergent flow pattern that existed during D₂
544 constitute typical features of extensional settings.

545 Díez Fernández (2011) provided a qualitative approach to the metamorphic
546 evolution of the relative autochthon of the study area. Conclusions regarding the
547 thermal evolution were in agreement with constraints obtained from regionally
548 equivalent sections located to the west (Gil Ibarguchi, 1982). Peak pressure in the upper
549 part of the Parautochthon has been recently estimated at 0.8 GPa at a temperature of
550 ~570 °C (Li and Massonne, 2017). Such pressure is in agreement with the regional
551 thickness of the overlying allochthon before extension and can be used as a reference
552 value at the onset of D₂. Temperatures during the last stages of D₁ were probably in the
553 range of ~550 °C to ~640 °C (staurolite stability field), but increased during the early
554 stages of D₂ as to produce partial melting and the growth of K-feldspar and sillimanite
555 in the metapelites. However, the growth of chlorite after sillimanite and andalusite
556 during the latest stages of S₂ development (Fig. 5b) and the greenschists facies
557 metamorphism that characterizes D₃ suggest an overall cooling metamorphic path
558 during D₂ and its transition to D₃. Cooling is accompanied by decompression, as
559 inferred from the growth of andalusite after sillimanite, and the growth of andalusite
560 following the development of a mid-pressure (0.8 GPa) mineral assemblage featured by
561 garnet, biotite and staurolite (Fig. 9b).

562 S₂ asymmetric structures support a component of simple shear during its
563 development (Passchier and Trouw, 2005). The stretching lineation is normal to the
564 vorticity vectors of such structures, as expected for monoclinic flow (Passchier, 1998).
565 S₂ probably formed in a transpressional flattening field (Dewey et al., 1998), as
566 suggested by the absence of L tectonites or general prolate planoliner fabrics (typical
567 for transtensional constrictional deformation), and by the dominance of S-L tectonites.
568 Accordingly, S₂ formed in a broad ductile shear zone characterized by general shear and
569 monoclinic flow.

570

571 *5.2. Regional implications*

572 The structural analysis carried out in this work reveals four (intra-D₂) stages in
573 the evolution of the Padrón dome after the emplacement of the allochthon (Fig. 10a).
574 The generation, segregation, and emplacement of melt in an extending crust define a
575 first stage (Fig. 10b). A second stage is characterized by the nucleation and
576 amplification of recumbent folds at the expense of the migmatitic banding, granitic
577 laccoliths, and pre-Variscan granites (Fig. 10c). Extension progressed while vertical
578 mass flow gained importance, thus favoring the upwarping of the region, and the
579 amplification of the domal structure during a third stage (Fig. 10d). As doming
580 progressed, discrete extensional faults cut across the previous structures during a fourth
581 stage (e.g., Pico Sacro detachment; Fig. 10e). This whole sequence of contrasting
582 structures represents a progressive development of processes related to extension and
583 doming, and some of them may have coexisted for a time. The fourth stage is followed
584 by the formation of upright folds in a compression-dominated setting (D₃; Fig. 10f). See
585 Díez Fernández and Pereira (2016) for a discussion about the transition from an
586 extension-dominated (D₂) to a compression-dominated (D₃) setting in the Iberian
587 Massif.

588 From a structural point of view, three types of granitoid massifs occur in the
589 Padrón migmatitic dome. The late-(post)kinematic massifs (not exposed in the study
590 area) cut all the planar fabrics observed in the dome. Their emplacement mechanism
591 introduces no pervasive ductile deformation into their country rocks. The syn-kinematic
592 massifs are associated with two contrasting phases of ductile deformation affecting their
593 metamorphic host (D₂ and D₃). D₂ syn-kinematic granitoids are characterized by low-
594 dipping planar fabrics parallel to those of their host (S₂). This particular group of

595 granitoids is related to post-collisional crustal extension. They occur in close relation to
596 migmatites and show sheet-like appearance. The emplacement-related structure of these
597 massifs may be severely modified by superimposed subhorizontal ductile flow (e.g.,
598 large D₂ recumbent folds). Solid-state deformation is widespread in them, but
599 heterogeneous regarding intensity. D₃ syn-kinematic massifs are dominated by near-
600 vertical planar fabrics. They represent intrusions associated with late Variscan strike-
601 slip tectonics, i.e. related to post-dome evolution and, eventually, to crustal thickening
602 (upright folds). Their planar fabrics are subparallel to the axial planes of local upright
603 folds or strike-slip shear zones. Those fabrics usually include a component of solid-state
604 deformation, but a component of magmatic origin is best preserved compared to D₂ syn-
605 kinematic granitoids.

606

607 *5.3. Rheological perspective on folding of granitoids*

608 Two complementary scenarios could explain the folding of the granitic massifs
609 along with their metamorphic host in the study area: (i) the massifs represented a readily
610 foldable mechanical anisotropy (rheological influence) shortly after intrusion (active
611 folding by initial buckling), and/or (ii) they were passively folded (no rheological
612 influence) along with the rest of the metamorphic series. For the case of D₂ syn-
613 kinematic granitoids, both scenarios would require that subhorizontal extensional flow
614 (general shear) remained long enough after intrusion as to produce the observed
615 isoclinal fold geometry.

616 Buckle folds require a mechanical anisotropy among the layers, either in the
617 form of a contrast in competence and/or sourced from a planar anisotropy such as a
618 foliation (Biot, 1965; Cobbold et al., 1971). The presence of mechanical instabilities,
619 such as rock bodies with irregularities and/or unlike effective viscosities, favors the

620 active nucleation of buckle folds by layer-parallel or layer-oblique shortening
621 (Ramberg, 1963; Treagus, 1973). Buckling plus superimposed flattening under general
622 shear may explain the formation of recumbent isoclinal folds (e.g., Hudleston, 1973;
623 Sanderson, 1982; Ramsay et al., 1983; Merle, 1986). Passive folding does not require
624 competence contrasts to occur, and is favored when no significant competence contrasts
625 exist among the layers. Since some of the geometrical features of folds depend on the
626 mechanisms by which they are formed (e.g., Ramsay and Huber, 1987; Ghosh, 1993;
627 Fossen, 2010), a discussion about whether the massifs were folded via active or passive
628 mechanisms could help to constrain the rheological and thermal state of the crust during
629 D₂ folding, i.e., shortly after voluminous melt was produced and vertical (diapiric) flow
630 was in place.

631 Active mechanisms of folding during early-D₂ should not be discarded for the
632 case of the orthogneisses of the Autochthon. A competence contrast between them and
633 the (weaker) surrounding paragneisses and migmatites would favor buckling as the
634 cause for nucleation of the recumbent folds near A Pereira (RP-11; Fig. 4).

635 In the study area, the competence differences between the metamorphic host
636 (schists, paragneisses and migmatites) and the D₂ syn-kinematic granitoids were
637 probably controlled by (i) mineralogy, (ii) grain size, (iii) pre-folding structure, and (iv)
638 temperature. (i) Feldspar-rich rocks would be more competent than mica-rich rocks. (ii)
639 Coarser grain-sized rocks are more competent than finer grain-sized rocks. (iii)
640 Pervasively foliated rocks would be less competent than non-foliated or weakly foliated
641 rocks. (iv) Solidified granitoid bodies differ mechanically from the host rock if they
642 have a higher temperature than the host. Young's modulus measures the stiffness of a
643 solid material, and depends on temperature. Magma bodies, either partially molten or
644 solidified, but still hot, would behave as soft inclusions relative to their host. A gross

645 comparison between the D₂ syn-kinematic granitoids and their metasedimentary rock
646 host suggests a less competent nature for the latter, which would be mica-rich and finer
647 in grain size, and probably would have well-developed foliation by the time granitoids
648 formed. Even though the granitoids had acquired a fabric during emplacement, such
649 anisotropy should be added to that/those the country rocks had already.

650 Despite the migmatites of the study area were folded under solid-state conditions
651 during D₂, there is no direct proof that the melt accumulated in the granitoid massifs had
652 crystallized by the onset of D₂ folding. It is uncertain whether the massifs of granitoids
653 represented actual competent layers that had actively contributed to the nucleation of the
654 Santa Comba antiform by buckling. Given the remarkable pre-fold sheet-like
655 appearance of the syn-kinematic granitoids, a planar anisotropy (e.g., magmatic fabric)
656 should be expected within the massifs after crystallization. A cornerstone to constrain
657 the timing of D₂ folding is the lack of folded penetrative planar anisotropies within the
658 granitoids. Apparently, D₂ folds were nucleated before the granitoids had acquired a
659 penetrative planar fabric, at least visible for the naked eye. The first (and main) fabric of
660 these massifs is axial planar to the D₂ folds. Consequently, that fabric must have been
661 configured during fold formation, most likely in the course of fold amplification.

662 The rheology of crystallizing magmas has been previously studied with a focus
663 on the transition from magmatic flow to submagmatic and solid-state deformation (e.g.,
664 Gapais and Barbarin, 1986; Blumenfeld and Bouchez, 1988; Miller and Paterson, 1994;
665 Büttner, 1999; Rosenberg and Handy, 2005). As magma crystallizes, its viscosity
666 increases (e.g., McBirney and Murase, 1984; Pitcher, 1993; Fernandez and Gasquet,
667 1994). But the viscosity of the granitic magma after melt generation and emplacement
668 (varying from a wholly liquid state to a stiffening suspension of crystals) is certainly
669 much lower than that of its metamorphic host. At that point, such a competence contrast

670 would not allow classical buckle folds to nucleate in a sheet-like intrusion (e.g., D₂ syn-
671 kinematic granitoids), as layer-parallel shortening would result in mullion-like
672 structures (Ramsay, 1967; Urai et al., 2001). Since there is no evidence of regular
673 cusped-lobate folds, with the cusps pointing towards the metamorphic host (the more
674 competent material before magma had crystallized), we must count on passive folding
675 for the nucleation of D₂ recumbent folds in the study area.

676 Passive folds have similar or sub-similar shape and rather uniform orientation of
677 cleavage in all parts (e.g., Santa Comba antiform). However, passive folding can take
678 place only if there is no significant competence contrasts among layers. Consequently,
679 passive folding at a large scale is less likely to have occurred shortly after melt
680 segregation/emplacement of D₂ granitic magmas. At that point, the rheology of the crust
681 would be affected by the presence of large (liquid) magma bodies such as the granite-
682 diatexite ensemble, which would be sites of reduced strength and could have induced
683 strain localization and increasing bulk transport rates along shear zones (e.g., Hollister
684 and Crawford, 1986; Davidson et al., 1992; Brown and Solar, 1998).

685 A crystallizing granitic magma creates a rigid framework that can accumulate
686 stress once the rigid percolation threshold (~55% crystals; Vigneresse et al., 1996) or
687 the critical melt percentage (~65% crystals; Arzi, 1978; van der Molen and Paterson,
688 1979) are reached. Rosenberg and Handy (2005) argued that the strength of melting
689 rocks does not differ much from that of crystallizing rocks undergoing deformation, i.e.
690 subjected to differential stress and finite strain. Accordingly, under relatively low melt
691 percentage, melt-bearing rocks can still localize strain along discrete shear bands (~93%
692 crystals, melt connectivity transition; Rosenberg and Handy, 2005). Any of these
693 thresholds could also represent a broad approximation to a reversal in competence

694 contrast, i.e. a switching point from a less competent to a more competent state of
695 granitic layers relative to their metamorphic host (e.g., Druguet and Carreras, 2006).

696 Isothermal crystallization is possible for ascending magmas that decrease their
697 H₂O concentration (degass) and thus increase their liquidus temperature. Typical for
698 shallow volcanic systems, lab experiments suggest that the mass fraction exclusively
699 crystallized by such mechanism seems relatively small (< 20%) at P ranging 0.1 GPa
700 (i.e., 3-4 km), reaching values that approach to the rigid percolation threshold (~55%
701 crystals) or to the critical melt percentage (~65% crystals) at P ranging 0.05 GPa
702 (Hammer and Rutherford, 2002). The thickness of the granite-diatexite ensemble before
703 recumbent folding can be estimated to a minimum of 1 km (Fig. 6), to which it should
704 be added the thickness of the overlying metamorphic host. Current exposures of that
705 host point to a thickness of ~1 km in the western flank of the Padrón dome (Figs. 4 and
706 6), although they could represent 2 to 3 km of extra thickness in the eastern flank (Díez
707 Fernández et al., 2012b, 2017). To this figure, it should be taken into account the
708 portion of overlying crust that has been removed by the Pico Sacro detachment
709 afterwards. The currently exposed fault line of this structure is more than 50 km long in
710 the NNW-SSE direction (Fig. 2), which corresponds to the moving direction of the fault
711 (Gómez Barreiro et al., 2010). That, combined with the oblique geometry of this normal
712 fault relative to the internal structure of its own footwall (e.g., Fig. 6), make us believe
713 that several km of the metamorphic host that was intruded by the granite-diatexite
714 ensemble are missing. Consequently, a minimum of 3 to 4 km of crust rested on top of
715 the granite-diatexite ensemble before being affected by recumbent folds. At that depth,
716 adiabatic crystallization would have played a rather minor role to increasing the
717 percentage of crystallized mass fraction. Alternatively, it is well established that magma
718 crystallizes as it cools, and it increases its effective viscosity (i.e., competence) as the

719 percentage of crystals increases. Therefore passive folding of the D₂ granitic massifs
720 seems constrained to a cooling path. In this regard, the overall metamorphic evolution
721 from D₂ (granulite facies conditions accompanied by partial melting) to D₃ (greenschists
722 facies conditions) suggests a progressive regional cooling during D₂. The growth of
723 chlorite after andalusite during the latest stages of S₂ development (Fig. 5b) is also in
724 agreement with this idea.

725 Interestingly, even if active mechanisms of folding (such as buckling) were in
726 part responsible for the formation of the D₂ recumbent folds, those mechanisms must
727 have operated on cooling granitic massifs too, as such massifs should be rigid enough to
728 make a competent layer relative to their country rocks. Textural observations made in
729 the granitic massifs suggest that their main planar fabric (S₂) probably resulted from
730 combining magmatic flow (aligned and imbricated feldspar) and solid-state flow
731 (internally deformed grains and generation of subgrains in quartz, feldspar and
732 plagioclase). This scenario is very likely when still melted continental crust reaches its
733 solidus while affected by superimposed deformation (e.g., Paterson et al., 1989; Vernon,
734 2000).

735 Passive folds result from accentuation of pre-existing curvatures. In the case of
736 the study area, previous folds (D₁?) or contacts of an irregular granitic massif may act as
737 favorable sites for passive fold nucleation. But the size of recumbent folds such as the
738 Santa Comba antiform needs a regional-scale approach to explain their development.
739 Migmatite domes usually show a history of competing forces (Whitney et al., 2004).
740 Vertical forces tend to compensate for inversion of gravity gradients sourced from an
741 underlying partially molten (lighter) crust. Subhorizontal (extensional) forces either
742 tend to attenuate lateral gravity gradients derived from thickened orogenic crust, and/or
743 they assist diapiric ascent of partially molten crust during orogenic collapse

744 (Vanderhaeghe et al., 1999; Vanderhaeghe, 2009). Under vertical flow dominance,
745 dome-like structures emerge, while subhorizontal channels are formed when
746 subhorizontal flow prevails. Fold nappes occur when vertical and lateral flow are
747 combined, but recumbent folds are favored if the rate of lateral flow is higher. A
748 progressive tilting of the partially molten crust driven by diapiric flow would be able to
749 bend (upward?) previous granitic laccoliths, thus facilitating passive folding under
750 dominant subhorizontal (extensional) flow (e.g., Harris et al., 2002; Arango et al.,
751 2013).

752 The contribution of diapiric flow to the formation of migmatitic domes is an
753 example of bending as a process of folding. Vertical and localized upward forces acting
754 across a regional subhorizontal layering, such as S_2 , would eventually result in a
755 regional dome or domes with which previous extension-related structures like D_2
756 recumbent folds and/or detachments interfere. This is the exact case of the Padrón
757 dome. In this regard, bending seems not restricted to the late stages of dome
758 development, as it probably contributed to the recumbent fold geometry of syn-
759 kinematic granitoids during passive folding (see above). However, bending is the
760 dominant mechanism during the advanced stages of dome evolution, i.e. before
761 detachment faults. Buckling, on the other hand, seems to have dominated during post-
762 extensional deformation (D_3). A colder orogenic crust featured by multiple crystallized
763 granitic massifs and contrasting lithologies is a favorable site for buckle folds to form
764 under compression. Passive folding in this setting is impeded by the existence of
765 widespread competence contrasts. The geometry and fabrics (crenulation cleavages)
766 related to D_3 suggest that many of the late upright folds were formed by buckling.

767 In the Padrón migmatitic dome, buckling concludes a sequence of folding
768 mechanisms that succeeded one another as a partially molten crust cooled.

769 Combinations of these mechanisms are likely to have occurred. In general terms,
770 between early passive folding (D_2) and late buckling (D_3), there is an intermediate stage
771 in which bending ruled and fostered the dome structure of Padrón.

772

773 **6. Conclusions**

774 Some of the syn-kinematic granitoids occurring in the northern part of the
775 Padrón migmatitic dome (NW Iberia) are deformed into large-scale, isoclinal recumbent
776 folds along with their metamorphic host. Recumbent folding is associated with
777 widespread, NNW-directed extensional flow, and accompanied by the development of
778 penetrative axial plane foliation. Partial melting giving way to the syn-kinematic
779 granitoids followed a stage of crustal thickening (continental collision). Post-thickening
780 extension operated on a thermally and gravitationally imbalanced lithosphere assisted
781 by: (i) partial melting and generation of crustal-derived magma (granitoids *s.l.*); (ii) the
782 inception of vertical diapiric flow and regional dome structures; (iii) subhorizontal flow,
783 which first flattened, stretched and folded syn-orogenic granitoids and their hosts, and
784 then favored the development of discrete extensional detachments.

785 Cooling produces rheological changes in a partially molten crust. One of the
786 most significant ones is a reversal in competence contrast between crystallizing melts
787 and their host. In this context, large-scale refolding structures in syn-orogenic granitoids
788 can be considered as an indicator of progressive cooling. Folding of large accumulations
789 of granitic melt is inhibited for a section of a partially molten crust that either maintains
790 or increases its temperature, thus impeding crystallization. A cooling path for a
791 continental crust featured by migmatites and granitic laccoliths favors folding of the
792 latter, either by active mechanisms (e.g., buckling) or passive mechanisms (passive
793 folding). In a partially molten crust subjected to progressive cooling and experiencing

794 magma crystallization, passive mechanisms of folding will likely occur before active
795 ones. Buckling requires a competence contrast between metamorphic host (less
796 competent) and crystallizing granitic magmas (more competent) that is reached later
797 than a more neutral state between them, which would favor passive folding. In this
798 regard, the fold interference between passive folds and later buckle folds observed in the
799 granitoids of the Padrón dome is compatible with progressive cooling.

800 Regional recumbent isoclinal folding of granitoid bodies defines a switching
801 point from which deep-seated orogenic crust, affected by dominant subhorizontal flow,
802 starts to cool down while it is exhumed along the core of migmatitic domes. An
803 eventual cooling path is inevitable during exhumation of high-grade metamorphic
804 domains, so granitoids intruding these domains are likely to develop folds if subjected
805 to post-granitoid emplacement ductile deformation. In cases where superimposed
806 deformation is intense, the structure of syn-orogenic granitoids would be poorly
807 conditioned by the processes related to melt generation, ascent and emplacement, but
808 largely controlled by superimposed deformation taking place afterwards, probably
809 during final cooling and crystallization.

810

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816

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1234 **Figure Captions**

1235 **Fig. 1-** Simplified map of the Variscan orogen after Martínez Catalán et al. (2007) and
1236 Díez Fernández and Arenas (2015). The location of the Padrón migmatitic dome is
1237 indicated.

1238

1239 **Fig. 2-** Simplified geological map and cross-section of the NW Iberian Massif (after
1240 Martínez Catalán et al., 2007; Díez Fernández et al., 2011). Location of the study area
1241 and insets to Figures 3a and 4 are indicated. Abbreviations: PSD – Pico Sacro
1242 detachment; BCD – Bembibre – Ceán detachment; RBD – Redondela – Beariz
1243 detachment.

1244

1245 **Fig. 3-** (a) Geological map (see regional location in Figure 2) and (b) cross-section of
1246 the northernmost part of the Padrón dome. Stereoplots with data from the northernmost
1247 section of the map shown in Figure 3a, containing (c) calculation of the Beta axis of D₃
1248 folds (F₃) using S₂ planes, Mean Principal Direction of D₃ fold axes (F₃), Mean
1249 Foliation Plane for S₃, and trend of D₃ stretching lineation (L_{3s}), and (d) showing the
1250 trend of D₂ stretching lineation (L_{2s}) and kinematics associated with D₂. Plots for the
1251 southern part are presented in Figures 6a and 6b. Reference Points or sites for
1252 understanding the geometrical analysis of the large-scale structures of the study area are

1253 indicated as RP-X in the map and cross-section. UTM coordinates (Zone 29). Plots are
1254 equal angle and lower hemisphere.

1255

1256 **Fig. 4-** Geological map of the northern part of the Padrón dome (see regional location in
1257 Figure 2). Reference Points or sites for understanding the geometrical analysis of the
1258 large-scale structures of the study area are indicated as RP-X in the map and cross-
1259 section. UTM coordinates (Zone 29).

1260

1261 **Fig. 5-** (a) Main foliation (S_2) of a migmatitic paragneiss containing sillimanite and K-
1262 feldspar (yellow colored). White mica is secondary. (b) Fragmented D_2 -Andalusite
1263 (And) porphyroblast containing an internal foliation with quartz + biotite + muscovite.
1264 Note the presence of staurolite (St) out of andalusite, and the growth of chlorite (Chl)
1265 between fragments of andalusite. (c) Main foliation (S_2) in the biotite orthogneisses. (d)
1266 Asymmetric, sigma-type lens of leucosome within a metatexite showing S_2 (regional)
1267 foliation. Note the oblique internal foliation within the leucosome lens. (e) Main
1268 foliation (S_2) of a granitoid sampled from the granite-diatexite ensemble. Note that the
1269 tectonic fabric was developed under solid-state conditions. (f) Main planar (subvertical)
1270 fabric (S_3) of the Negreira syn-kinematic granodiorite.

1271

1272 **Fig. 6-** Cross-section of the northern part of the Padrón dome showing the folded
1273 structure of some syn-kinematic granitic massifs and their metamorphic host, as
1274 opposed to that of the late-kinematic granodiorites. Locations of the sections are
1275 indicated in Figure 4.

1276

1277 **Fig. 7-** Stereoplots with data from the southern section of the map shown in Figure 3a,
1278 containing (a) calculation of the Beta axis of D_3 folds (F_3) using S_2 planes, Mean
1279 Principal Direction of D_3 fold axes (F_3), Mean Foliation Plane for S_3 , and trend of D_3
1280 stretching lineation (L_{3s}), and (b) the trend of stretching lineation (L_{2s}) and kinematics
1281 associated with D_2 . (c) Stereoplot with data from the northernmost section of the map
1282 shown in Figure 4, showing the Mean Principal Direction of D_3 fold axes (F_3), Mean
1283 Foliation Plane for S_3 , and trend of D_3 stretching (L_{3s}) and mineral lineation (L_{3m}).
1284 Stereoplots with data from the southern and central part of the map shown in Figure 4,
1285 containing (d), the Mean Principal Direction of D_3 fold axes (F_3), Mean Foliation Plane
1286 for S_3 , and trend of D_3 stretching (L_{3s}) and mineral lineation (L_{3m}), (e) the trend of
1287 stretching (L_{2s}) and mineral lineation (L_{2m}), and kinematics associated with D_2 , and (f)
1288 calculation of the Beta axis of D_3 folds (F_3) using S_2 planes. Plots are equal angle and
1289 lower hemisphere.

1290

1291 **Fig. 8-** (a) Andalusite-bearing metatexite showing folded layers (white dashed line) and
1292 sigma-type structures (top-to-the-NNW). Note the variable orientation of the internal
1293 foliation in the andalusite porphyroblasts. (b) Leucosome lenses in the metatexites
1294 affected by isoclinal folds, to which the main foliation (S_2) is axial planar. (c)
1295 Migmatitic layering of a diatexite affected by upright (D_3) folds. (d) Penetrative
1296 foliation (S_2) in the granitoids of the granite-diatexite ensemble (zoom in the down left
1297 corner). (e) Folded granitic dike intruded into metatexites. The main foliation (S_2) is
1298 axial planar to the folds. (f) Foliation plane in andalusite-bearing metatexites. Note the
1299 stretching lineation (L_{2s}) defined by quartz (white dashed line), and its parallelism with
1300 the preferred mineral lineation marked by andalusite porphyroblasts.

1301

1302 **Fig. 9-** (a) Delta-type structure defined by the external and internal foliation in an
1303 andalusite porphyroblast (rolling fabric). (b) D₂-andalusite porphyroblast containing an
1304 internal foliation with quartz + biotite + muscovite + staurolite + opaques (metatexite).

1305

1306 **Fig. 10-** Tectonic evolution of the northern central part of the Padrón dome. (a)
1307 Collision and crustal thickening (D₁) caused by the emplacement of the Allochthon onto
1308 its relative autochthon (Parautochthon and Autochthon). Note that the Basal, Upper, and
1309 Ophiolitic allochthonous units are gathered into a single unit referred to as Allochthon.
1310 (b) Development of shallow-dipping foliation (proto-S₂), partial melting, and granitic
1311 bodies during the early stage of orogenic collapse (early-D₂). (c) N-NW-directed
1312 extensional flow and formation of recumbent folds (axial plane foliation, S₂) during
1313 intermediate stage of orogenic collapse (intermediate-D₂). (d) Progressive tilting of the
1314 northern flank of the Padrón dome (advanced-D₂). (e) Development of extensional
1315 detachments (top-to-the N-NW kinematics) during the late stage of orogenic collapse
1316 (late-D₂). (f) Renewed crustal thickening (D₃) featured by upright folds, subvertical
1317 crenulation cleavage (S₃), and accompanied by further syn-orogenic magmatism.

1318

EUROPEAN VARISCIDES

(CROPPING OUT / COVERED)

Figure 1- Simplified map of the Variscan orogen after Martínez Catalán et al. (2007) and Díez Fernández and Arenas (2015). The location of the Padrón migmatitic dome is indicated.

Figure 2- Simplified geological map and cross-section of the NW Iberian Massif (after Martínez Catalán et al., 2007; Díez Fernández et al., 2011). Location of the study area and insets to Figures 3a and 4 are indicated. Abbreviations: PSD – Pico Sacro detachment; BCD – Bembibre – Ceán detachment; RBD – Redondela – Beariz detachment.

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